

Kinetics of chlorination of phenol and monosubstituted phenols by *t*-butyl hypochlorite in aqueous alkaline medium

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The kinetics of chlorination of the parent and sixteen monosubstituted phenols (2-chloro, 2-methyl, 2-carboxy, 2-nitro, 3-chloro, 3-methyl, 3-carboxy, 4-fluoro, 4-chloro, 4-bromo, 4-methyl, 4-ethyl, 4-methoxy, 4-carboxy, 4-acetyl and 4-nitro) by *t*-BuOCl have been studied in aqueous alkaline medium. The rates of reactions show first order kinetics each in [*t*-BuOCl] and [XC₆H₄OH] and inverse first order in [OH⁻]. Variation in either ionic strength or addition of reaction product has no significant effect on the rates of reactions, while lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. The rates are measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters for all the phenols computed. A mechanism involving the electrophilic attack of phenoxide ions by HOCl in the rate determining step is suggested. The rates decrease in the order : 3-CH₃ > 2-CH₃ > 4-OCH₃ > 4-CH₃ > 4-C₂H₅ > H > 3-Cl > 3-COO⁻ > 4-F > 2-COO⁻ > 4-Br > 2-Cl > 4-Cl > 4-COO⁻ > 4-COCH₃ > 2-NO₂ > 4-NO₂. Hammett equation of the type, $\log k = -3.44 - 2.35 \rho$ is found to be valid for substituent effects. The enthalpy and entropy of activation are correlated.

The halogens – fluorine, chlorine, bromine and iodine form an important group of elements which exist not only in their well known diatomic molecular forms but also as atoms, ions and in covalent combination with many other elements^{1,2}. In a number of reactions, halogen molecules act as sources of positive halogens for coordination with electron-rich centres. The well characterized electrophilic chlorinating agent containing Cl-O bond is *t*-butyl hypochlorite which is widely used for both homolytic and heterolytic chlorinations. In hydroxylic solvents, *t*-BuOCl serves as a source of positive chlorine³ resulting in electrophilic addition to alkenes and substitution of arenes. It is also used for the preparation of a number of *N*-chloro derivatives and as an oxidizing agent^{1,4}. The chemistry of phenols is of importance from several angles. Phenol chemistry is dominated by the nucleophilicity of the system and its propensity for varied reactions with a wide range of electrophiles^{5,6}. Thus, a lot of work needs to be done before attempting to generalize the phenol reactions and the effect of substituents on them. Keeping these facts in view, we report herein the kinetics of chlorination of phenol and 16 monosubstituted phenols by *t*-BuOCl in alkaline medium.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of chlorination of phenol and sixteen monosubstituted phenols (2-chloro, 2-methyl, 2-carboxy, 2-nitro, 3-chloro, 3-methyl, 3-carboxy, 4-fluoro, 4-chloro, 4-

bromo, 4-methyl, 4-ethyl, 4-methoxy, 4-carboxy, 4-acetyl and 4-nitro phenols) by *t*-BuOCl in aqueous alkaline medium have been studied under varying [*t*-BuOCl], [substrate], [OH⁻], [Cl⁻], solvent composition and temperature.

*Effect of varying [*t*-BuOCl]* : At constant [substrate]₀ (5–50 fold excess over [*t*-BuOCl]₀) and [OH⁻], first order plots of log [*t*-BuOCl] vs time were linear up to at least 75% completion of the reactions. The pseudo-first order rate constants remained unaffected by the changes in [*t*-BuOCl]₀ (Tables 1 and 2), establishing first order dependence of the rate on [*t*-BuOCl], in all the cases.

Effect of varying [phenol] : At constant [*t*-BuOCl]₀ and [OH⁻], under substrate excess conditions (5–50 fold), the rates increased with increase in [substrate] with a first order dependences with all the phenols (Tables 1 and 2). The plots of *k*_{obs} vs [phenols] were linear with zero intercepts on the ordinates.

Effect of varying other parameters of the medium : The rates decreased with increase in [OH⁻], at fixed [*t*-BuOCl]₀ and [phenol] with an inverse first order kinetics in [OH⁻] for the chlorination of all the phenols (Tables 1 and 2). The plots of *k*_{obs} vs 1/[OH⁻] gave straight-lines passing through the origin. Variation in ionic strength of the medium (0–0.50 mol dm⁻³) or addition of the product, *t*-BuOH (0.0–0.01 mol dm⁻³) had negligible effect on the rates of chlorination. But the decrease in dielectric constant of the

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the chlorination of the substituted phenols by *t*-BuOCl (ROCl) in aqueous alkaline medium

$10^3[\text{ROCl}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{S}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{eff}}^a$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{) for X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OH where X =$							
			H ^b	2-CH ₃ ^b	2-Cl ^d	2-COO ^{-c}	2-NO ₂ ^e	3-CH ₃ ^b	3-Cl ^d	3-COO ^{-d}
0.3	2.0	8.0	3.6	15.7	2.3	2.7	0.52	-	9.3	6.1
0.4	2.0	8.0	3.6	15.7	2.1	2.7	0.52	29.0	9.1	6.0
1.0	2.0	8.0	3.6	15.8	1.9	2.7	0.52	28.9	9.0	6.0
2.0	2.0	8.0	3.7	15.9	1.9	2.7	0.51	28.6	8.9	6.0
3.0	2.0	8.0	3.7	15.9	1.9	2.7	0.51	28.2	8.8	5.9
1.0	0.5	8.0	0.86	4.0	0.45	0.75	0.13	7.2	1.9	1.4
1.0	1.0	8.0	1.8	8.0	0.98	1.4	0.25	14.0	4.3	2.8
1.0	2.0	8.0	3.6	15.8	1.9	2.7	0.52	28.9	9.0	6.0
1.0	3.0	8.0	5.5	23.1	2.9	3.9	0.76	37.9	13.1	9.2
1.0	5.0	8.0	10.0	36.4	5.2	6.8	1.3	-	23.3	16.2
1.0	2.0	3.0	10.6	44.8	5.2	4.4	1.5	-	20.2	17.0
1.0	2.0	5.0	6.0	29.5	3.2	3.5	0.88	-	13.6	9.8
1.0	2.0	8.0	3.6	15.8	1.9	2.7	0.52	28.6	9.0	6.0
1.0	2.0	10.0	2.7	11.7	1.5	-	0.42	24.1	6.0	4.8
1.0	2.0	20.0	1.5	6.5	0.82	2.0	0.20	12.9	3.2	2.4
1.0	2.0	30.0	0.85	3.6	0.50	1.7	-	8.6	2.3	-

$$^a[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{eff}} = [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{total}} - [\text{phenol}].$$

Temp. : ^b238, ^c288, ^d298, ^e318 K.**Table 2.** Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the chlorination of the *para*-substituted phenols by *t*-BuOCl (ROCl) in aqueous alkaline medium

$10^3[\text{ROCl}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{S}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{eff}}^a$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{) for X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OH where X =$								
			4-CH ₃ ^b	4-C ₂ H ₅ ^b	4-OCH ₃ ^b	4-COCH ₃ ^f	4-COO ^{-d}	4-F ^c	4-Cl ^d	4-Br ^e	4-NO ₂ ^g
0.3	2.0	8.0	8.4	-	-	5.0	2.1	2.9	2.0	-	0.34
0.5	2.0	8.0	8.3	7.2	11.8	5.0	2.1	2.9	1.9	3.1	0.34
1.0	2.0	8.0	8.3	7.1	12.0	5.0	2.1	2.9	1.7	3.1	0.33
2.0	2.0	8.0	8.3	7.0	12.0	5.1	2.1	-	1.7	3.1	0.33
3.0	2.0	8.0	8.2	7.0	12.1	5.1	2.1	2.9	1.7	3.2	0.33
1.0	0.5	8.0	2.0	1.8	3.1	1.1	0.5	0.61	0.42	0.84	0.09
1.0	1.0	8.0	4.0	-	-	2.3	1.0	1.4	0.93	1.6	0.18
1.0	2.0	8.0	8.3	7.1	12.0	5.0	2.1	2.9	1.7	3.1	0.33
1.0	3.0	8.0	13.0	10.6	18.5	7.6	3.1	-	2.6	-	0.49
1.0	5.0	8.0	20.1	19.0	30.5	12.2	4.8	8.0	4.3	8.4	0.80
1.0	2.0	2.0	-	31.0	46.6	18.0	-	10.2	-	11.8	1.30
1.0	2.0	3.0	24.0	21.0	32.1	12.0	6.7	-	4.4	7.8	0.80
1.0	2.0	5.0	14.4	21.0	19.3	8.0	3.8	4.2	2.6	-	0.52
1.0	2.0	8.0	8.3	7.1	12.0	5.0	2.1	2.9	1.7	3.1	0.33
1.0	2.0	10.0	7.7	5.0	9.40	-	1.7	2.4	1.3	2.4	0.28
1.0	2.0	20.0	3.5	2.9	4.6	2.1	0.9	-	0.65	1.3	-
1.0	2.0	30.0	2.1	-	-	-	-	-	0.47	-	-

$$^a[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{eff}} = [\text{OH}^-]_{\text{total}} - [\text{phenol}].$$

Temp. : ^b283, ^c288, ^d293, ^e298, ^f313, ^g318 K.

Table 3. Activation parameters for the chlorination of phenol and monosubstituted phenols by *t*-BuOCl in alkaline medium

Parameter	H	2- CH ₃	2- Cl	2- COO ⁻	2- NO ₂	3- CH ₃	3- Cl	3- COO ⁻	4- CH ₃	4- C ₂ H ₅	4- OCH ₃	4- COCH ₃	4- COO ⁻	4-F Cl	4- Br	4- NO ₂	
log <i>A</i>	8.9	10.3	10.1	9.1	10.6	8.2	10.3	11.5	10.9	7.5	9.4	9.8	11.6	10.0	9.6	6.7	10.1
<i>E_a</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)	67.0	68.0	77.3	69.6	90.5	58.0	73.1	82.7	76.0	65.3	66.9	78.5	85.6	74.5	74.9	58.2	87.7
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	64.6	67.6	72.8	68.5	87.7	55.7	72.0	84.1	75.1	63.4	64.8	76.1	81.2	72.0	72.5	55.0	85.2
ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-82.2	-58.4	-67.5	-75.2	-51.8	-98.4	-58.1	-28.8	-38.5	-80.8	-71.3	-65.4	-28.2	-62.2	-68.7	-127.5	-63.3
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	87.9	84.4	92.6	90.1	104.2	83.5	89.5	89.7	86.0	86.3	86.3	96.5	92.1	89.6	91.9	93.0	103.1

medium by the addition of *t*-BuOH (5–40%, v/v) increased the rate. The plots of log *k* vs % *t*-BuOH were linear.

Fig. 1. Plot of log *k_{obs}* vs σ ; $10^3 [t\text{-BuOCl}]_0 = 50$ $[\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}]_0 = 12.5$ $[\text{OH}^-] = 2.0$, $l = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 283 K.

The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been calculated from the following relationships (Table 3),

$$\log k = \log A - E_a/2.303 R (1/T)$$

$$\log (k/T) = \log (k_B/h) + \Delta S^\ddagger/2.303 R - \Delta H^\ddagger/2.303 R (1/T)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger$$

In alkaline solutions, *t*-BuOCl exists as OCl⁻,

Phenols also exist as phenoxide ions in alkaline solutions,

Hence OCl⁻ and phenoxide ions (S) were used to represent *t*-BuOCl and phenols, respectively.

The observed kinetics of first order each in [*t*-BuOCl] and [phenol] and inverse first order in [OH⁻] may be explained by the mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

where S' is the chlorinated product.

Scheme 1

The rate law in accordance with Scheme 1, is given by eqn. (3),

$$-\frac{d[t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [t\text{-BuOCl}][\text{S}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (3)$$

Eqn. (3) may be rearranged as

$$-\frac{1}{[t\text{-BuOCl}]} \frac{d[t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (4)$$

But we have

$$-\frac{1}{[t\text{-BuOCl}]} \frac{d[t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = \frac{d \ln [t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}}$$

Eqn. (4) therefore takes the form,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (5)$$

The plots of *k_{obs}* vs [S] or 1/[OH⁻] were linear with zero intercepts on the ordinates, in accordance with the rate law (5). Further, the constant *K₁* for the equilibrium,

was calculated from the dissociation constant, *K_a* ($2.95 \times$

10^{-8})⁷ of HOCl and the ionic product of water, K_w (10^{-14}) as $K_a = [H^+][OH^-]$ and

$$\frac{K_w}{K_a} = \frac{[HOCl][OH^-][H_2O]}{[OCl^-][H_2O]}$$

$$= K_1[H_2O] = \frac{1.0 \times 10^{-14}}{2.95 \times 10^{-8}} = 3.39 \times 10^{-7}$$

and hence

$$K_1 = \frac{3.39 \times 10^{-7}}{[H_2O]} = \frac{3.39 \times 10^{-7}}{1000/18}$$

$$= \frac{3.39 \times 10^{-7}}{55.56} = 6.1 \times 10^{-9}$$

The values of k_2 for all the phenols were calculated from the slopes of either k_{obs} vs $[S]$ or k_{obs} vs $1/[OH^-]$ plots.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [H_2O]}{[OH^-]} \text{ and slope} = K_1 k_2 [H_2O][S] \text{ or}$$

$$k_2 = \frac{\text{slope} \times [OH^-]}{K_1 [H_2O]} \quad k_2 = \frac{\text{slope}}{K_1 [H_2O][S]}$$

where $[OH^-]$ and $[S]$ are the standard run concentrations.

Two sets of k_2 values were calculated for all the phenols from the slopes of the plots, k_{obs} vs $[ArO^-]$ and k_{obs} vs $1/[OH^-]$ and the values agree very well. The k_2 values calculated from the former plots are $10^{-3} k_2$ ($dm^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) = 4.7, 17.2, 0.78, 0.11, 0.009, 30.0, 3.7, 2.4, 9.4, 8.9, 14.4, 0.23, 0.67, 2.0, 0.67, 4.1, 0.006 for the parent and 2-CH₃, 2-Cl, 2-COO⁻, 2-NO₂, 3-CH₃, 3-Cl, 3-COO⁻, 4-CH₃, 4-C₂H₅, 4-OCH₃, 4-COCH₃, 4-COO⁻, 4-F, 4-Cl, 4-Br, 4-NO₂ substituted phenols, respectively.

There was a wide variation in rates with the change of substituents. The rate constant changes by a factor of about 5.2×10^3 . The rate is fastest with methyl group in the *meta*-position and is slowest with the nitro group in the *para*-position. Therefore, the reactions had to be studied at different temperatures for different substituted phenols depending on the rates of the reactions with the substituents (Tables 1 and 2). Hence for the purpose of comparison, the rates of all the substituted phenols were computed for 283 K by the relationship,

$$\log k = \log k_{obs} + \frac{E_a}{2.303 R} \frac{283 - T}{283 T} \quad (6)$$

The energies of activation computed by the Arrhenius plots

were used (Table 3). The calculated pseudo-first order rate constants (k) at 283 K are $10^4 k_{obs}$ (s^{-1}) = 3.6, 15.8, 0.62, 1.6, 0.008, 28.9, 3.0, 1.8, 8.3, 7.1, 12.0, 0.20, 0.61, 1.7, 0.57, 0.89 and 0.006 for the parent and 2-CH₃, 2-Cl, 2-COO⁻, 2-NO₂, 3-CH₃, 3-Cl, 3-COO⁻, 4-CH₃, 4-C₂H₅, 4-OCH₃, 4-COCH₃, 4-COO⁻, 4-F, 4-Cl, 4-Br and 4-NO₂ substituted phenols, respectively, at $10^3 [t\text{-BuOCl}]_0 = 50 [S] = 12.5 [OH^-]_{eff} = 2.0$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (where I is ionic strength).

As may be seen, the rate constant for the *meta*-methyl substituted phenol is the highest at $28.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($10^3 [t\text{-BuOCl}]_0 = 50 [S]_0 = 12.5 [OH^-] = 2.0$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and lowest at $0.0055 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the *para*-nitro substituted phenol. Introduction of electron-donating groups such as CH₃, OCH₃ etc., increases the electron density in the ring by both resonance and inductive effects. Hence the rates of substituted phenols with these groups are higher. The rates are lower for phenols with electron-withdrawing groups. Further, the rate of a *meta*-substituted phenol is higher than the *ortho*- or *para*-substituted phenol for the same group as both *ortho* and *para* positions are open for chlorination with these monosubstituted phenols.

Validity of Hammett equation for the chlorination of phenol by *t*-BuOCl has also been tested (Fig. 1). The following equation is found to be valid for *para*-substituted phenols,

$$\log k_{obs} = 3.44 - 2.35 \sigma \quad (r = 0.98) \quad (7)$$

Variation in rate within a reaction series is due to the changes in either or both the enthalpy and entropy of activations. Reasonable correlation of these for the reaction of all the substituted phenols indicate that the changes in rate are caused by changes in both ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger and the latter vary in a parallel fashion (Table 3).

The observed increase in rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium may be explained by the Laidler and Eyring⁸ equation. This equation (8) has been deduced based on electrostatic interactions, for the rate constant of a reaction between a neutral dipolar molecule A with a dipole moment μ_A and anion B bearing charge Z_B ,

$$\ln k_D = \ln k_\alpha + \frac{Z_B^2 e^2}{2 k_B T D} \left[\frac{1}{r_B} - \frac{1}{r_\ddagger} \right] \quad (8)$$

where k_D and k_α are the rate constants in the media of dielectric constants D and α , respectively, r_B and r_\ddagger refer to the radii of the reactant species and the activated complex, respectively. It is evident from eqn. (8) that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when r_\ddagger

$> r_B$. It is probable that the radii of the activated complexes in the present cases are greater than the reactant molecules, as the reactions involve the interaction between negative ions and the dipolar molecule.

A detailed mechanism of chlorination is shown in Scheme 2. As the phenoxide ion is highly resonance stabilized in alkaline solutions, electrophilic substitution takes place at both *ortho* and *para* positions.

Scheme 2

Experimental

t-BuOCl was prepared⁹ in good purity by chlorinating aqueous solution of *t*-BuOH (29.6 g) in the presence of sodium hydroxide (15 g) and sodium carbonate (3 g). The resulting *t*-BuOCl layer was separated, washed with sodium carbonate solution and water. The compound was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. It distilled in the temperature range 350–351 K. Purity of the compound was checked further by the iodometric determination of active chlorine present. A stock solution of *t*-BuOCl (0.01 mol dm⁻³) in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide was prepared, standardized and stored in dark coloured bottles. Stability of the oxidant was checked at regular intervals. The concentration remained unchanged for more than 72 h.

Pure samples of all the phenols were distilled or recrystallized before use. Stock solutions of the phenols (0.10 mol dm⁻³) in 0.10 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide were prepared as and when required. Preliminary investigations revealed that the addition of chloride did not have significant effect on the rates of reactions. Hence the ionic strength of the medium (*I*) was maintained at 0.50 mol dm⁻³ using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium chloride.

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [phenol] \gg [*t*-BuOCl] (5–50 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of *t*-BuOCl (0.0003–0.003 mol dm⁻³), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to mixtures containing known amounts of phenol (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), sodium hydroxide (0.01–0.30 mol dm⁻³),

sodium chloride and water, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric determination of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within +3%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of *t*-BuOCl – phenols reactions were determined by allowing the reaction mixtures containing phenol and *t*-BuOCl in 1 : 1 molar ratio in aqueous sodium hydroxide to completion at room temperature. The observed stoichiometry may be represented as

The chlorinated phenoxide ion was characterized as follows. The reaction mixtures were acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The brown layers separated were removed, washed with water and distilled. The presence of chlorine in the product phenol was confirmed by Lassaigne's test¹⁰. Further, the aqueous layer of the reaction products did not give test for the free chloride ion. *ortho/para* ratio of the chlorinated products was found pH and solvent dependent⁵. But in the case of chlorination of *ortho*- or *para*-substituted phenols, the site of attack would be either *para* or *ortho* position, respectively, while with *meta* substituted phenols, varying proportions of *ortho* and *para* products are expected, as in the case of the parent phenol.

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